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SHEEHAN'S SYNDROME WITH PANCYTOPENIA

متلازمة شيهان مترافقة مع قلة الكريات الشاملة في الدم

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ملخص الحالة

متلازمة شيهان بالتعريف هي قصور في النخامى الأمامية متفاوت الشدة يحدث نتيجة تنخر إقفاري تالٍ للولادة في الغدة النخامية بعد نزف هائل. تلاحظ الاضطرابات الدموية كفقر الدم سوي الصباغ عند هؤلاء المرضى، إلا أن من النادر ملاحظة قلة الكريات الشاملة pancytopenia. سيتم في هذا التقرير تقديم حالة امرأة سورية بعمر 35 سنة راجعت بمظاهر قصور نخامي، أظهرت الفحوصات المخبرية قلة كريات شاملة، تمت معالجتها بالمعالجة الهرمونية المعيضة المناسبة. يجب أن يأخذ الأطباء السريريون بالاعتبار القصور النخامي كسبب محتمل لقلة الكريات الشاملة.

ABSTRACT

Sheehan's syndrome is defined by varying degrees of anterior pituitary deficiency due to postpartum ischemic necrosis of the pituitary gland after massive bleeding. Hematologic abnormalities such as normochromic anemia have been reported in these patients. However, pancytopenia is rarely observed. We describe the case of a 35-year-old Syrian woman with features of hypopituitarism. Laboratory tests showed pancytopenia that was completely reversed after adequate hormone replacement. Clinicians should consider the possibility of hypopituitarism as a cause of pancytopenia.

INTRODUCTION

Sheehan's syndrome (SS) is a parturition-related pituitary disease resulting from severe postpartum hemorrhage and can present with varying degrees of pituitary insufficiency.¹ It is a rare complication of postpartum hemorrhage first described in 1937.²

Sheehan's syndrome is rare probably due to migrant

women and unawareness of physicians regarding the syndrome. From another side diagnosis of SS has often been overlooked and thus delayed for long years due to its nonspecific signs and symptoms.¹ Most common presenting symptoms of Sheehan's syndrome are lactational failure, prolonged amenorrhea or oligomenorrhea after delivery.^{3,4} The most frequent hematologic finding is normochromic anemia in Sheehan's syndrome.^{5,6} Pancytopenia is rarely observed in patients with Sheehan's syndrome.^{5,7,8}

Signs and symptoms: Signs and symptoms of Sheehan's syndrome occur because of the deficiencies of the various hormones the pituitary gland controls: thyroid, adrenal, breast milk production and menstrual function. It can present during postpartum period or several months or years following delivery. The mean duration between postpartum bleeding and the subsequent development of symptoms varies from 1 to 33 years.^{1,9} Patient usually present with lactation failure following delivery (this was the first thing direct us to the case when we start studying it), cessation of menstrual periods, generalized weakness and debility, premature

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wrinkling of the forehead and face, genitals and body hair loss, and coarse dry skin. Rare clinical presentation includes acute circulatory collapse, congestive cardiac failure, hypoglycemia (which occurs 2 times with our patient), diabetes insipidus, or psychosis.¹

Epidemiology: The prevalence of SS has not been exactly defined due to the great number of undiagnosed patients as we remark at the beginning of the article. In 1965, Sheehan estimated that the worldwide prevalence was 100-200 per 100,000 women.^{1,10} In 1996, the World Health Organization estimated that 100,000 women were dying each year due to SS, and more than 3 million women in the world were suffering from SS.^{1,11} In the Kashmir region of India, the prevalence of SS was found to be 3.1% among women in 2005, and two thirds of women were still giving birth at home.¹²

In Turkey, a recent study investigating the causes of hypopituitarism reported the frequency of SS as 27.6% among 338 female patients, making SS the second most common cause of hypopituitarism in females.¹³ In a retrospective study from the Philippines in 2010, analysis of the data of 82 female patients with hypopituitarism revealed that in 14% of patients the underlying etiology was SS.¹⁴ In the USA, hypopituitarism was not detected in the follow-up of 55 women with histories of severe PPH between 1998 and 2002.¹⁵ Similarly, in an investigation of 404 patients with pituitary disease in the UK, only one case was reported to have SS.¹⁶ However, it appears that SS is not as rare as assumed in Western society, probably due to the migrant women who gave birth in their home countries.^{1,17} Accordingly, the prevalence of SS was found to be 2.6 per 100,000 women in the northwestern region of Spain¹⁸ in 1999 and 5.1 per 100,000 women in Iceland in 2009.¹⁹

CASE PRESENTATION

A 35-year-old Syrian woman was urgently sent to our Hematology department with confusion, vomiting, and diarrhea. A low blood pressure was observed (80/45 mmHg). An initial laboratory test showed pancytopenia, which was the major reason to send her to our department. Her leukocyte count was $0.76 \times 10^9/L$ with a neutrophil count of $0.31 \times 10^9/L$. Her hemoglobin level

was 8.8 g/dL with mean corpuscular volume MCV at 91.96 fL, mean corpuscular hemoglobin MCH at 28.43 pg and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration at 30.92 g/dL. Her platelets count was at $58 \times 10^9/L$. Her serum ferritin level was normal at 151.4 ng/mL. A bone marrow aspiration revealed normocellular to slightly hypocellular. Chest X-ray and abdominal ultrasound were normal. A detailed interview revealed that she had excessive bleeding in the course of her first delivery age of 25 years. She talks about anemia after every delivery. In addition, history of lactation failure and no resumption of menstruation following the childbirth was present. She complained of significant fatigability and weakness after the childbirth. A physical examination showed pallor and rough skin. Her breast tissue was normal but the areolae were depigmented. She had no pubic or axillary hair. Pituitary hormone studies were compatible with a status of primary pituitary insufficiency (Table 1). Her follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) was at 2.56 $\mu IU/ml$, free thyroxine (FT4) was low at 0.425 $\mu g/dl$ with an inadequate level of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) at 0.688 $\mu IU/ml$. Her basal serum cortisol (measured at 8 a.m.) was at 1.12 $\mu g/dL$, her prolactin level was 1.8 ng/ml.

The diagnosis of Sheehan's syndrome was established in the background of appropriate history and hormonal studies and pituitary magnetic resonance images corroborated it by demonstrating a normal-sized sella that was flat with no pituitary parenchyma inside. There was no abnormality in hypothalamic, supra sellar, or para-sellar regions in the MRI, (Figure 1).

She received replacement therapy with L-thyroxine 100 $\mu g/day$ and hydrocortisone 300 mg/day IV divided q8hr, started with a dose of 20 mg/kg/day, later the dose increased as no improvement of her symptoms had occurred. In fact, the hematologic abnormality had dramatically improved. A follow-up after a week of that high dose of hydrocortisone revealed complete normalisation of her haematological parameters. Her leukocyte count was $4.1 \times 10^9/L$, her hemoglobin level was 10.1 g/dL and her platelets count was $219 \times 10^9/L$. Unfortunately, the patient died with a complete AV block before discharging and that happen after sudden electrolyte imbalance.

Case	Ref	Hb	TLC	MCV	MCH	MCHC	PLT	Reticulocyte
		g/dL	TLC×10 ⁹ /μl	fL	pg	g/dL	PLT×10 ⁹ /μl	%
1	3	9	3.4	87	31	36	71	0.4
2	1.4	6.5	2.3	85	33	35	96	0.2
3	1.5	7.5	3.42	96.6	32.8	33.8	70	0.9
4	6	9	2.3	-	-	-	90	0.3
5	1.7	9.2	3.2	94.2	30.7	32.4	64	0.3
6	1.7	10.6	3.4	82.2	26.4	32.1	74	0.5
7	1.7	9.8	3.2	94.8	33.1	31.6	42	0.2
8	1	7.9	3	87.7	32	30	92	-
9 our case		8.8	0.76	91.96	28.43	30.92	58	0.4

Table 1. Hematological anomalies in previously published cases and our patient.

Figure 1. Empty Sella.

DISCUSSION

The diagnosis of Sheehan’s syndrome is determined by the patient’s history and physical examination, and confirmed by laboratory tests which prove anterior pituitary failure. Laboratory tests can reveal many other anomalies such as electrolyte imbalances. Cortisol deficiency, hypothyroidism and volume depletion are the main causes of that. It also seems that Sheehan’s syndrome has hematological consequences, to which

little attention is paid because of their rarity. Anemia is well recognized as a feature of hypopituitarism. Gokalp et al. have recently reported hematological abnormalities in 65 patients with Sheehan’s syndrome, 80% of whom presented with anemia, compared with 25% of controls.²⁰ Many hormonal deficiencies, such as hypothyroidism, adrenal insufficiency and gonadal hormonal deficiency, can explain normochromic anemia in hypopituitarism.²¹ However, within the framework of hematologic disorders, pancytopenia is rarely observed in patients affected with Sheehan’s syndrome. The first case was reported by Ferrari et al. in 1975.²² A bone marrow aspiration was carried out showing normocellularity to slight hypocellularity and decreased hemopoiesis, decreased erythropoiesis but no decreased granulopoiesis. (bone marrow piobsy was refused by the patient). Pancytopenia as a result of an anterior hormone deficiency has not been clearly investigated. It is a consequence of the loss of effect of pituitary hormones on metabolic reactions to hematoipoiesis, which is related to hypopituitarism. Treatment with thyroxine and glucocorticoides lead to full hematological recovery in all published cases. For our patient, hematological recovery was obtained after 9 days and that was so unusual!

CONCLUSIONS

Hematologists need to be aware of Sheehan’s syndrome as a treatable etiology of pancytopenia in women.

Consent: Written informed consent was obtained

from the brother of patient for publication of this manuscript, and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

Authors' contributions: DF analyzed and interpreted the patient data regarding the endocrinological disease, and was a major contributor in writing the manuscript. Both AF and DF analyzed and interpreted the patient data regarding the hematological disease. Both authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. Diri H, Karaca Z, Tanriverdi F, et al. Sheehan's syndrome: new insights into an old disease. *Endocrine* 2016 Jan 1;51(1):22-31.
2. Bhattacharya K. A case of Sheehan's syndrome developing mania following low dose corticosteroid therapy. *Clin Psychiatr* 2015.
3. Aggarwal HK, Jain D, Pawar S, et al. Recurrent hypoglycaemia: an uncommon presentation in Sheehan syndrome. *Eur J Gen Med* 2016 Apr;13(2):155-7.
4. Schrager S, Sabo L. Sheehan syndrome: a rare complication of postpartum hemorrhage. *J Am Board Fam Pract* 2001 Sep;14(5):389-91.
5. Demir MV, Yaylaci S, Demir TÖ, et al. A rare cause of pancytopenia: Sheehan's syndrome. *Med J Dr. DY Patil Univ* 2015 Mar;8(2):265.
6. Gokalp D, Tuzcu A, Bahceci M, et al. Sheehan's syndrome as a rare cause of anaemia secondary to hypopituitarism. *Ann Hematol* 2009 May;88(5):405-10.
7. Ozbey N, Inanc S, Aral F, et al. Clinical and laboratory evaluation of 40 patients with Sheehan's syndrome. *Isr J Med Scien* 1994 Nov;30(11):826-9.
8. Kim DY, Kim JH, Park YJ, et al. Case of complete recovery of pancytopenia after treatment of hypopituitarism. *Ann Hematol* 2004 May;83(5):309-12.
9. Huang YY, Ting MK, Hsu BS, et al. Demonstration of reserved anterior pituitary function among patients with amenorrhea after postpartum hemorrhage. *Gynecol Endocrinol* 2000 Jan;14(2):99-104.
10. Sheehan HL. The frequency of post-partum hypopituitarism. *BJOG: An Intern J Obstet Gynaecol* 1965 Feb;72(1):103-11.
11. Adamson P. The progress of nations 1996, commentary: a failure of imagination. UNICEF 1996 (1996). <http://www.unicef.org/pon96/womfail.htm>. Accessed 11 June 1996
12. Zargar AH, Singh B, Laway BA, et al. Epidemiologic aspects of postpartum pituitary hypofunction (Sheehan's syndrome). *Fertil Steril* 2005 Aug;84(2):523-8.
13. Tanriverdi F, Dokmetas HS, Kebapci N, et al. Etiology of hypopituitarism in tertiary care institutions in Turkish population: analysis of 773 patients from pituitary study group database. *Endocrine* 2014 Sep;47(1):198-205.
14. Aimee A, Jay S, Leilani B, et al. Clinical profile and etiology of hypopituitarism at the University of Santo Tomas Hospital. *Phil J Internal Med* 2012 Aug;48(3):23-8.
15. Feinberg EC, Molitch ME, Endres LK, et al. The incidence of Sheehan's syndrome after obstetric hemorrhage. *Fertil Steril* 2005 Oct;84(4):975-9.
16. Toogood A, Shalet S. GH deficiency and the degree of hypopituitarism. *Clin Endocrinol* 1995 Apr;42(4):443-4.
17. Tessnow AH, Wilson JD. The changing face of Sheehan's syndrome. *Am J Med Sci* 2010 Nov;340(5):402-6.
18. Regal M, Páramo C, Sierra JM, et al. Prevalence and incidence of hypopituitarism in an adult Caucasian population in northwestern Spain. *Clin Endocrinol* 2001 Dec;55(6):735-40.
19. Kristjansdottir HL, Bodvarsdottir SP, Sigurjonsdottir HA. Sheehan's syndrome in modern times: a nationwide retrospective study in Iceland. *Eur J Endocrinol* 2011 Mar;164(3):349-54.
20. Fatma M, Mouna E, Nabila R, et al. Sheehan's syndrome with pancytopenia: a case report and review of the literature. *J Med Case Rep* 2011 Oct;5(1):490.
21. Huang YY, Ting MK, Hsu BS, et al. Demonstration of reserved anterior pituitary function among patients with amenorrhea after postpartum hemorrhage. *Gynecol Endocrinol* 2000 Jan;14(2):99-104.
22. Ferrari E, Ascari E, Bossolo PA, et al. Sheehan's syndrome with complete bone marrow aplasia: Long-term results of substitution therapy with hormones. *Br J Haematol* 1976 Aug;33(4):575-82.